

Analysis of matrix-dominated failure in thermoplastic composites and conduction welded joints

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Abstract

Thermoplastic composites have facilitated novel manufacturing methodologies, such as conduction welding, with the intent of enhancing the sustainability of the aviation sector. This advancement concurrently offers substantial advantages for cost-effective high-volume production. An integral aspect of welding involves diminishing the requirement for mechanical fasteners. However, the absence of fasteners presents new challenges, as the effectiveness of these heavily loaded structural connections is depending upon the performance of the thermoplastic polymer matrix. Currently, there exists a limited comprehension of the mechanisms underlying the failure of welded joints in thermoplastic materials. Moreover, the numerical and experimental approaches, initially designed and validated for thermoset composites, have not been comprehensively assessed for thermoplastic composites. Additionally, the manufacturing process conditions for these innovative structures possess the potential to significantly impact the mechanical performance of the material, thus assuming a pivotal role in the design of thermoplastic composite structures.

The objective of this research is to analyze matrix-dominant failures in thermoplastic composites and conduction-welded joints with the aim to develop both experimental and numerical methodologies that can facilitate the design of thermoplastic composite structures such as the Multi-Functional Fuselage Demonstrator as shown in Figure 1 [1].

Figure 1: Conduction welding of the Multi-Functional Fuselage Demonstrator [1]

Initially, the accuracy of continuum damage models in predicting matrix failures and ply separations is investigated, considering these failure modes as pivotal for welded joints. Two methodologies are incorporated into a novel continuum damage model, based on different stress-strain measurements. The initial approach relies on small strain increments, while the latter method incorporates large deformation kinematics. Evaluation of the methodology encompasses numerical benchmarks at varying levels: (1) single element; (2) unidirectional single-ply open-hole specimens; and (3) open-hole composite laminate coupons. The significance of the methodology accommodating large deformation kinematics within the constitutive model is underscored, particularly when predicting ply-splitting matrix failures. This methodology [2] enhances the overall capabilities of Virtual Testing [3] for both thermoset and thermoplastic composites and establishes a foundation for high-fidelity analyses of welded joints as shown in Figure 2 [4] and thermoplastic composite structures [5].

The adoption of innovative manufacturing processes and fastener-free assembly techniques in thermoplastic composites accentuates the reliance on interlaminar behavior for structural performance, while empirical data remains limited. Consequently, the interlaminar properties of autoclave-consolidated AS4D/PEKK-FC thermoplastic composites are characterized [6]. This is achieved through analyses involving Mode I, Mode II, and Mixed Mode I/II at 50:50 tests, with considerations for fiber bridging and R-curve effects. Test configurations are adjusted to account for the large fracture process zone ahead of the crack tip, ensuring stable crack propagation. An appropriate data reduction methodology is selected. Experimental data is then processed using an inverse methodology coupled with a novel procedure to directly input cohesive laws in tabular format into commercial finite element software, based solely on load-displacement curves. The cohesive laws' profiles offer new insights into the influence of fiber bridging on interlaminar behavior [6,7]. Fractographic analysis of interlaminar damage mechanisms confirms the substantial impact of fiber bridging coupled with significant plastic deformation on fracture surfaces.

Leveraging the mixed-mode interlaminar properties [7] and the continuum damage model [2], the strength and failure characteristics of welded joints are investigated, both through numerical simulations and empirical testing. To this end, a conduction-welded single-lap shear joint is manufacture, produced, and analyzed. Two distinct modeling approaches are presented for analysis: a simplified model encompassing only damage at the welded interface, and a high-fidelity ply-by-ply approach accounting for physical failure mechanisms at the lamina level. The high-fidelity modeling methodology accurately predicts the experimental failure mode of the welded joints, underscoring that joint strength is significantly influenced not only by the failure mechanisms at the welded interface but also by those of the adjacent plies. Nevertheless, the interlaminar properties established through autoclave consolidation prove inadequate in predicting the joint strength, with the likeliest source of disparity attributed to localized alterations in material properties resulting from the welding process [4].

Figure 2: Welded single-lap shear final failure modes: a) Numerical; b) Experimental [4]

In order to address this mismatch, a methodology is formulated to characterize and analyze thermoplastic composite conduction welded joints, with consideration for the manufacturing process's impact. Test specimens are manufactured from welds using a half-meter long welding tool. Special emphasis is placed on weldability, given the complexities associated with welding typical unidirectional characterization specimens. Furthermore, a 0-degree interface is adopted to ensure that fracture exclusively occurs at the welded interface. Characterization tests encompass Double Cantilever Beam and End-Notched Flexure tests on two distinct specimen configurations employing several welding parameters. While full weld width specimens offer insights into weld quality, those extracted from the center of the weld are deemed most representative for characterizing the welded joint material properties. The manufacturing process's influence becomes evident in Single Lap-Shear joints due to variations in weld size, which is also confirmed tensile and three-point-bending experimental results. Ultimately, the characterized material properties are incorporated into numerical analyses to appraise the efficacy of the cohesive zone modeling approach in predicting the strength of the welded joints.

In summary, this research extensively examines matrix-dominated failures in thermoplastic composites and conduction-welded joints, resulting in the formulation of multiple experimental and numerical methodologies that support the design of thermoplastic composite structures. These methodologies yield new insights into the intricate interactions among manufacturing processes, mechanical properties of thermoplastic composites, and the quality and failure behavior of conduction-welded joints [1].

References

1. B. H. A. H. Tijs, Analysis of thermoplastic composites and conduction welded joints, Ph.D. thesis, Delft University of Technology, Delft, the Netherlands (5 2023).
2. B. H. A. H. Tijs, C. G. Dávila, A. Turon, and C. Bisagni. The importance of accounting for large deformation in continuum damage models in predicting matrix failure of composites. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 164:107263, 1 2023.
3. O. Falcó, R. L. Avila, B. Tijs, and C. S. Lopes. Modelling and simulation methodology for unidirectional composite laminates in a Virtual Test Lab framework. *Composite Structures*, 190:137–159, 4 2018.
4. B. H. A. H. Tijs, M. H. J. Doldersum, A. Turon, J. E. A. Waleson, and C. Bisagni. Experimental and numerical evaluation of conduction welded thermoplastic composite joints. *Composite Structures*, 281:114964, 2 2022.
5. K. S. van Dooren, B. H. A. H. Tijs, J. E. A. Waleson, and C. Bisagni. Skin-stringer separation in post-buckling of butt-joint stiffened thermoplastic composite panels. *Composite Structures*, 304:116294, 1 2023.
6. B. H. A. H. Tijs, S. Abdel-Monsef, J. Renart, A. Turon, and C. Bisagni. Characterization and analysis of the interlaminar behavior of thermoplastic composites considering fiber bridging and R-curve effects. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 162:107101, 7 2022.
7. S. Abdel-Monsef, B.H.A.H. Tijs, J. Renart, and A. Turon. Accurate simulation of delamination under mixed-mode loading using a multilinear cohesive law. *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, 284:109233, 5 2023.

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